

Effect of *a priori* coordinate errors on the abscissa solution

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From some of the earliest Copenhagen set simulations (Petersen, 1982 Aug 7) it has been known that a priori errors of the adjusted coordinates (abscissa = U , ordinate = ρ) to some extent propagate into the abscissa solution. This note gives an analytical treatment of the phenomenon.

Since the abscissae (U) are subject to adjustment, it is clearly only the errors in the perpendicular coordinate, with mean error ϵ_ρ , that matter. The effect can be understood as follows (see Fig. 1). Let R , Z , and S be respectively the pole of the reference great circle, the instantaneous scanning pole, and a star. In the course of a set (12 h interval), the point Z moves approximately along a great circle arc passing through R , thus producing a scanning node N at 90° from R and Z . It is expedient to assume that N is a fixed point and the origin of set coordinates ($U_N = \rho_N = 0$). Now if S is observed while the scanning pole is at Z , the measurement effectively locates the star on the great circle arc ZS . The angle from Z , $90^\circ - \zeta$, is however not measured but computed from the attitude knowledge (position of Z) and the a priori star ordinate ρ . Clearly, if the latter is in error by $\Delta\rho$, the transverse field coordinate will be in error by $\Delta\zeta \simeq \Delta\rho$, due to the small value of the angle at S . Consequently, when inferring the abscissa from this measurement, it will be in error by $\Delta U \simeq \Delta\rho \sin e \cos U$, where e is the small angle RZ . In fact, a strict calculation yields, for $\zeta = 0$,

$$\frac{dU}{d\rho} = \tan e \cos U \quad (1)$$

The point S may however be scanned several times during the set, each time with a different scanning pole and a different e . We can assume that the final abscissa error is simply the average of the errors resulting from the individual scans, i.e.

$$\Delta U = \Delta\rho \langle e \rangle \cos U \quad (2)$$

with the average $\langle \rangle$ being taken over all scans in the set passing over S . This $\langle e \rangle$ depends on the coordinates of S , (U, ρ), and on the total arc traversed by Z .

The angles of the spherical triangle ZRS are approximately related by

$$\zeta = \rho + e \sin \nu \quad (3)$$

The point $S = (\nu, \rho)$ is observable only when $|\zeta| \leq f$, with f being half the transverse FOV. The corresponding range of e -values is

$$\frac{-f - \rho}{\sin \nu} \leq e \leq \frac{f - \rho}{\sin \nu} \quad (4)$$

For reasons of symmetry we need only consider the principal octant ($\rho \geq 0$, $0 \leq \nu \leq 90^\circ$). But the scanning pole only moves over an arc of length E on both sides of R , i.e.

$$-E \leq e \leq E \quad (5)$$

so that the actual range of "observability" for point S is

$$e_{\min} \leq e \leq e_{\max} \quad (6)$$

with

$$e_{\min} = \max(-E, \frac{-f - \rho}{\sin \nu}) \quad (7a)$$

$$e_{\max} = \min(E, \frac{f - \rho}{\sin \nu}) \quad (7b)$$

Assuming that the various scans across S are uniformly distributed over the permitted range (6) we get

$$\langle e \rangle = \frac{1}{2}(e_{\min} + e_{\max}) \quad (8)$$

or

$$\langle e \rangle = \begin{cases} 0, & E \sin \nu \leq f \wedge \rho \leq f - E \sin \nu \\ -\rho / \sin \nu, & f \leq E \sin \nu \wedge \rho \leq E \sin \nu - f \\ (-\rho + f - E \sin \nu) / (2 \sin \nu), & |f - E \sin \nu| \leq \rho \leq f + E \sin \nu \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The contribution to the abscissa variance (after set solution) is

$$\sigma_U^2(\varepsilon_\rho) = \sigma_U^2(0) + \langle e \rangle^2 \cos^2 U \varepsilon_\rho^2 \quad (10)$$

We are in particular interested in the average variance contribution for all stars in the set. Thus we compute the average factor in (10),

$$\frac{\overline{\langle e \rangle^2 \cos^2 U}}{\langle e \rangle^2 \cos^2 U} = \frac{\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}\pi} \cos^2 U \, dU \int_0^{\rho_{\max}} \langle e \rangle^2 \, d\rho}{\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}\pi} dU \int_0^{\rho_{\max}} d\rho} \quad (11)$$

where the half-width of the covered section of the sky is given by

$$\rho_{\max} = f + E \sin U \quad (12)$$

according to (3). The denominator in (11) is the solid angle of the covered octant,

$$\int_0^{\frac{1}{2}\pi} dU \int_0^{\rho_{\max}} d\rho = \frac{1}{2} \pi f + E \quad (13)$$

(actually a factor $\cos \rho$ is neglected). In the numerator, we first have

$$\int_0^{\rho_{\max}} \langle e \rangle^2 \, d\rho = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{3} E^3 \sin U, & \sin U \leq f/E \\ \frac{1}{3} E^3 \sin U + fE^2 - \frac{f^2 E}{\sin U} + \frac{f^3}{3 \sin^2 U}, & \sin U \geq f/E \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Dividing by $\rho_{\max}$, taking the squareroot, and multiplying by $\cos U$, we get the factor $e_{\text{rms}} \cos U$ as function of abscissa; see Fig. 2. For typical values of E and f it is stars at abscissae $10^\circ - 45^\circ$ that are most strongly affected.

Below we assume that $f \leq E$. Performing the second integration in (11) we get

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\langle e \rangle^2 \cos^2 \psi} &= \frac{E^2}{1 + \pi x/2} \left[\frac{1}{9}(2-y^3) + \frac{x}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2}{3}x^2\right) \arccos(x) + \frac{5}{6}x^2 y + x^2 \ln \frac{x}{1+y} \right] \\ &= E^2 g^2(x) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where

$$x = f/E, \quad y = (1 - x^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (16)$$

The function $g(x)$ is tabulated hereafter.

x	$g(x)$
0.0	0.3333
0.1	0.3767
0.2	0.3822
0.3	0.3753
0.4	0.3636
0.5	0.3506
0.6	0.3375
0.7	0.3252
0.8	0.3138
0.9	0.3034
1.0	0.2941

For a set of duration T_s and with revolving velocity $v_z = de/dt$ we have

$$E = \frac{1}{2} v_z T_s \quad (17)$$

Nominally, $T_s = 12$ h, $v_z = 11-13$ am/h, $f = 0.45$ deg, so that $x = 0.34-0.41$ and $g(x) \approx 0.366$. Then

$$\sigma_U^2(\epsilon_\rho) \approx \sigma_U^2(0) + (0.183 v_z T_s \epsilon_\rho)^2 \quad (18)$$

A comparison with Copenhagen simulations is given in the table below. It appears from this comparison that (18) slightly overestimates the effect; better agreement is obtained with the semi-empirical formula

$$\sigma_U^2(\epsilon_\rho) \approx \sigma_U^2(0) + (0.174 v_z T_s \epsilon_\rho)^2 \quad (19)$$

Set ID	T_s (h)	v_z (am/h)	h_{00}	g_{01}	σ_{att} (as)	ϵ_ρ (as)	σ_U (mas)	quadratic difference: actual predicted (18)	
M-1	12	11	0.001	1.0	0.2	0.5	3.7	} 3.34 mas	3.51 mas
B-5	12	11	0.001	1.0	0.2	0.1	1.6		
B-1	12	11	0.001	1.0	0.04	0.5	3.6	} 3.32 mas	3.51 mas
B-2/3	12	11	0.001	1.0	0.02/6	0.1	1.4		
S-4	3	11	0.001	1.0	0.0	0.5	2.0	} 0.87 mas	0.88 mas
S-5	3	11	0.001	1.0	0.0	0.0	1.8		

Application: Copenhagen Set Simulation M-11

For this run we have $T_s = 12$ h, $v_z = 13$ am/h and $\epsilon_\rho = 0.5$ as (Zeis 82-11-05, MAT-HI_-03613). Relative to a more realistic coordinate error, $\epsilon_\rho = 0.1$ as (after the preliminary all-sky reduction), the abscissa variance should be increased by 14.96 mas^2 according to (19). Subtracting this from the actual abscissa dispersions in the various magnitude intervals, we find by analysis similar to NDAC/LO/017,

$$H = 1.70 \qquad h = 0.52 \qquad (20)$$

This assumes $\langle n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \rangle = 0.178$ and $\sigma_\eta(B, \tau)$ as in the table below.

B	N(B)	$\sigma_\eta(B, \tau)$	$\sigma_U(.5)$	$\sigma_U(.1)$
5 - 6	62	3.13 mas	4.89 mas	2.99 mas
6 - 7	105	4.73	4.59	2.48
7 - 8	275	6.74	4.13	2.10
8 - 9	887	9.47	5.15	3.40
9 - 10	342	13.3	5.31	3.64
10 - 11	274	18.6	6.33	5.01
11 - 12	127	27.0	6.66	5.42
12 - 13	35	39.8	9.35	8.51
all	2107	12.0 mas	5.32 mas	3.63 mas

